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Review Article

A REVIEW ON FLUOROQUINALONES**Mrs. Sheeja Rekha A. G *, Dr. Prasobh G.R, Mr. Nishad V.M, Mrs. Athira A.S,
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Thiruvananthapuram Dist, Kerala**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

*Lower respiratory tract infection is a common condition associated with considerable morbidity and mortality. The management of lower respiratory tract infection is complicated by the increasingly recognized spectrum of pathogens associated with this disease and their antibiotic susceptibility patterns. Fluoroquinolone antibiotics have a wide spectrum of activity that covers the common respiratory pathogens. However, the perceived limitations of older fluoroquinolones against *S. pneumoniae* have led to a reluctance to use these agents in respiratory tract infection. The newer fluoroquinolones retain the good activity against Gram-negative organisms and "atypical" respiratory pathogens of older agents, while providing extended Gram-positive activity.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Lower respiratory tract infection is a common condition associated with considerable morbidity and mortality. The management of lower respiratory tract infection is complicated by the increasingly recognized spectrum of pathogens associated with this disease and their antibiotic susceptibility patterns. Disease management guidelines for respiratory tract infection are a relatively recent occurrence. Pathogens commonly associated with lower respiratory tract infection include Haemophilus influenzae, Streptococcus pneumoniae and Moraxella catarrhalis, with atypical organisms playing a significant aetiological role in pneumonia. Increasing antibiotic resistance in these pathogens has led to concerns about the efficacy of currently available antibiotics.

The treatment of lower respiratory tract infection in the community is largely empirical, as identification of the causative pathogen is seldom undertaken. First-line therapies for acute bacterial exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) commonly include amoxicillin, a cephalosporin or, in some countries, a macrolide. However, as 25% of patients return within 1 week, the efficacy of such therapy is questionable.

Development of antimicrobials for clinical use has been most successful in targeting essential components of 5 general areas of bacterial metabolism: cell wall synthesis, protein synthesis, RNA synthesis, DNA synthesis, and intermediary metabolism. The quinolones are a family of synthetic broad-spectrum antibiotics. The term quinolone(s) refers to potent synthetic chemotherapeutic antibacterials [1]. Quinolones comprise a relatively large, growing and most interesting group of antibacterial drugs which have made a major impact on the field of antimicrobial chemotherapy, particularly in the past few years

Fluoroquinolone antibiotics have a wide spectrum of activity that covers the common respiratory pathogens [9,10]. However, the perceived limitations of older fluoroquinolones against *S. pneumoniae* have led to a reluctance to use these agents in respiratory tract infection. The newer fluoroquinolones retain the good activity against Gram-negative organisms [11, 12] and "atypical" respiratory pathogens of older agents, while providing extended Gram-positive activity. Of particular interest is their activity against *S. pneumoniae*, irrespective of penicillin susceptibility, and β -lactamase-positive and negative strains of *H. influenzae* and *M. catarrhalis*

Due to their potency, broad activity spectrum, oral bioavailability and generally good safety profile, fluoroquinolones have been used extensively for multiple clinical indications worldwide. Quinolones have been prescribed to treat UTIs, respiratory tract infections (e.g. community-acquired and nosocomial pneumonia, chronic bronchitis and tuberculosis), skin and soft tissue infections, bone and joint infections, intra-abdominal infections, sexually transmitted diseases, among others. However, due to the extensive use of these drugs in human and veterinary medicine, and despite prescribing guidelines now recommending reserving quinolone use, the number of quinolone-resistant strains has been growing steadily, being observed in all species treated by this antimicrobial class.

With the recent introduction of agents such as gatifloxacin and moxifloxacin, the traditional gram-negative coverage of fluoroquinolones has been expanded to include specific gram-positive organisms. The new fluoroquinolones are rarely first-line agents and should be employed judiciously. Inappropriate use of agents from this important class of antibiotics will likely worsen current problems with antibiotic resistance.

Mechanisms of Quinolone action

Quinolones act by inhibiting the activity of two essential bacterial type II topoisomerases, DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, which are involved in the modulation of the chromosomal supercoiling required for DNA synthesis, transcription and cell division. These enzymes modulate DNA topology by passing an intact double helix through a transient 4 bp staggered double-stranded break that they introduce in a separate segment. In order to preserve genomic integrity during this process, DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV form covalent bonds between active site tyrosine residues and the 5'-overhangs at the DNA break, forming enzyme-cleaved DNA complexes known as cleavage complexes. Quinolones interfere with this critical process by reversibly binding to these cleavage complexes at the enzyme-DNA interface in the cleavage-ligation active site, therefore increasing the steady-state concentration of cleavage complexes by physically blocking DNA strand religation. Quinolone-topoisomerase binding was recently demonstrated to occur through a water-metal ion bridge, where a noncatalytic Mg²⁺ ion coordinated with four water molecules forms a bridge for hydrogen bonding between the quinolone and the serine and acidic residues that act as anchor points to the enzyme^{1,4,9,10}. DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV are A2B2 heterotetramer enzymes composed of two pairs of

identical subunits, GyrA2 GyrB2 and ParC2ParE2 (or GrlA2GrlB2), respectively. Despite their general functional and structural similarities, DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV have distinct physiological functions. DNA gyrase uses the energy of ATP hydrolysis to actively introduce negative supercoils into DNA which are essential for

- (i) setting the super-helical density that allows chromosome condensation,
- (ii) relieving the torsional stress that accumulates in front of replication forks and transcription complexes, and
- (iii) promoting local melting for transcript initiation by RNA polymerase.

Topoisomerase IV also plays a role in maintaining chromosomal super-helical density and alleviating torsional stress, although to a lesser extent than DNA gyrase since it is only able to relax positive supercoils and unable to introduce further negative supercoiling.

However, the major function of topoisomerase IV is decatenation of the interlocked daughter chromosomes at the end of replication^{1,4,6,10}.

Quinolones are known to target DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV with varying efficiencies in different bacterial species. Generally, DNA gyrase is considered the primary target of quinolones in Gram-negative species and topoisomerase IV the primary target in Gram-positives. However, this has been proven to be untrue in many cases, with examples of Gram-positive species where DNA gyrase is the primary target for quinolones and also cases of different quinolones having distinct primary targets in the same species or quinolones with similar potencies against both enzymes. Hence, the relative contribution of each topoisomerase to quinolone action still needs further investigation, on a species-by-species and drug-by-drug basis, in order to be fully elucidated^{1,4,9}.

Quinolones: Mechanism of Action

The formation of quinolone–topoisomerase–DNA ternary complexes causes the DNA replication machinery to become arrested at blocked replication forks, resulting in an inhibition of DNA synthesis, which immediately leads to bacteriostasis (at low quinolone concentrations) and eventually to cell death (at lethal concentrations)^{6,10}. Due to the positioning of DNA gyrase ahead of the DNA replication complex and of topoisomerase IV behind it, it appears that the interaction of quinolones with DNA gyrase results in a more rapid inhibition of DNA replication than with topoisomerase IV^{9,11}. Moreover, when DNA tracking systems (replication forks, transcription complexes, etc.) collide with these stabilized ternary complexes, permanent chromosomal breaks are generated^{5,4}. These doublestrand DNA breaks trigger the bacterial DNA stress response, in which the RecA protein is activated by DNA damage and promotes

the self-cleavage of the LexA repressor, thus depressing the expression of SOS response genes such as DNA repair enzymes. The quinolone bactericidal activity therefore results from the overwhelming of these processes and the extent to which DNA repair is incomplete. Indeed, fluoroquinolone bactericidal activity has been shown to be enhanced when the induction of the SOS response is prevented.

The contribution of reactive oxygen species to quinolone-mediated cell death has been recently shown to occur in a protein synthesis-dependent manner¹². This suggests that, in addition to the inhibition of DNA replication, other events that may affect DNA or other cellular damage may also contribute to the bactericidal activity of quinolone drugs; however, the underlying molecular mechanisms are not yet fully understood⁹. Moreover,

inhibition of the catalytic functions of DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV due to quinolone stabilization of cleavage complexes results in a loss of enzyme

activity that affects a number of nucleic acid processes and is therefore likely to contribute to the overall toxicity of quinolones⁵.

Classification

Based on spectrum of activity

Quinolone generations	Drugs	Microbiological activity	Administration and characteristics	Indications
First generation	Nalidixic Acid (NegGram) Cinoxacin	Enterobacteriaceae	Oral administration, low serum and tissue drug concentrations, narrow gram-negative coverage	uncomplicated urinary tract infections, not for use in systemic infections
Second generation	Class I Lomeflaxcin Norfloxacin Enoxacin	Enterobacteriaceae	Oral administration, low serum and tissue drug concentrations, improved gram negative coverage compared to first generation quinolones, limited gram positive coverage	uncomplicated urinary tract infections, Not for use in systemic infections
	Class II Ofloxacin Ciprofloxacin	Enterobacteriaceae, atypical pathogens; Pseudomonas aeruginosa (ciprofloxacin only)	Oral and intravenous administration, higher serum, tissue and intracellular drug concentrations compared with class I agents coverage of atypical pathogens	Complicated urinary tract and catheter-related infections, Gastroenteritis with severe diarrhea, Prostatitis, Nosocomial infections, STD's
Third generation	Levofloxacin Sparfloxacin Gatifloxacin Moxifloxacin	Enterobacteriaceae, atypical pathogens, streptococci	Oral and intravenous administration, similar to class II second generation quinolones but with modest streptococcal coverage	Similar indications as for second generation quinolones, community acquired pneumonia in hospitalized patients.
Fourth generation	Trovafloxacin	Enterobacteriaceae, atypical pathogens, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, methicillin susceptible Staphylococcus aureus, streptococci, anaerobes	Oral and intravenous administration, similar to third generation quinolones but with improved gram-positive coverage and added anaerobic coverage	Consider for treatment of intraabdominal infections.

The newer quinolones have enhanced activity against staphylococci, streptococci and anaerobes. In general, the older generation compounds have more activity against gram negative bacteria and provide less gram positive coverage. The 3rd and 4th generation quinolones show an expanded spectrum of activity against gram positive organisms. In regards to their activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, moxifloxacin and gatifloxacin demonstrate more potent *in vitro* activity than ciprofloxacin or levofloxacin.

Of these agents ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin and moxifloxacin. They have activity against a broad range of gram positive and negative organisms. The drugs in this class are uniformly active against the Enterobacteriaceae, and many strains of *Listeria*, *Chlamydia*, and mycobacteria

CHEMISTRY

A quinolone antibiotic is a member of a large group of broad-spectrum bacteriocidals that share a bicyclic

core structure related to the substance 4-quinolone. Nearly all quinolone antibiotics in use are fluoroquinolones, which contain a fluorine atom in their chemical structure and are effective against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria.

STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIPS

All clinically important compounds of fluoroquinolone class are synthetic fluorinated analogues of naldixic acid, a 1,8-naphthyridine and possess a 4-quinolone nucleus

The structure-activity relationships (SAR) of quinolones.

The pharmacophore required for significant antibacterial activity is 4-pyridone-3-carboxylic acid with a ring at 5 or 6 position.

Now considerable information is available about the effects of modifications on nucleus. Although various alterations were done to improve antibacterial activity two major pathways of lead optimization of original 1,8 naphthyridine nucleus were pursued. Both the strategies are based on modification of 6-fluoro and 7-piperazinyl quinolone.

It is pertinent to mention here that a similarity is seen in many fluoroquinolones with beta lactams, wherein a reciprocal relationship is seen in both the classes where an increase in Gram positive activity is associated with a decrease in Gram negative activity. The first route of lead optimization involved replacement of nitrogen atom by carbon atom at position-8, as well as other side chain modifications, resulting in fluoroquinolones such as 1-cyclopropyl (ciprofloxacin) and 1,8-cyclo compounds such as ofloxacin and levofloxacin (6). Additional molecular substitution at 6-fluoro, 7-piperazinyl yielded second generation agents with improved activity and pharmacokinetic profile, such as sparfloxacin and clinafloxacin. These compounds demonstrated greatly improved activity against many Gram-positive species without compromising on their activity against Gram negative bacteria, contrary to the earlier agents of this class.

The second major route of chemical modifications retained the naphthyridine core, yielding agents such as enoxacin and tosufloxacin. The 7-azabicyclo evolutionary modification lead to third generation molecule of trovafloxacin, which showed, increased spectrum of antibacterial activity and also improved potency.

The essential features for improving lead compound of fluoroquinolone class (Fig. 2) are summarized below:

4-Oxo group is essential for the activity.

Reduction of 2, 3- double bond eliminates the activity.

Position 1 (nitrogen in ring A): The side chain attached to ring nitrogen significantly affects the potency of the drug. The earlier compounds such as naldixic acid, pipemidic acid, norfloxacin, enofloxacin, cinoxacin, rosoxacin etc. had an ethyl group as side chain at the nitrogen atom. So the optimal substituent at position one appeared to be ethyl, but cyclopropyl and difluorophenyl have resulted in increased potency.

Addition of some small group at cyclopropyl, as fluorine in case of fleroxacin, results in overall improved activity against Gram positive bacteria.

Replacement of cyclopropyl group of ciprofloxacin by an oxetane (compound A) had increased Gram positive activity relative to ciprofloxacin.

Connecting the methoxy or hydroxy group at carbon-8 atom to a dimethylamino group at nitrogen-1 atom displayed superior *in vitro* and *in vivo* antibacterial activity as compared to ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin in addition to having good bioavailability (94%) and half-life of 4.6h.

Position 2 and 3: One part of the molecule where modifications are rarely attempted is at positions 2 and 3.

The carboxylic moiety at position 3 is believed to be the portion of the pharmacophore that binds to the DNA gyrase of the bacterial cell, and thus it is important do not interfere with the stereochemistry around this area.

Generally, modification of the 3-carboxylic acid group produced compounds with decreased activity. However, some attempts have been made where incorporation of an aldehyde (formaldehyde) group at

carbon-3 position, as well as certain labile carboxylate esters afforded derivatives, which displayed antibacterial properties, but the activity was due to their conversion (*in vivo*) to corresponding carboxylic acids. Replacement of 3-carboxyl group with isothiazole group produced the most potent isothiazquinolone, which have 4 to 10 times greater *in vitro* antibacterial activity than ciprofloxacin, but it appeared to suffer from some undesirable properties such as insolubility and mammalian toxicity.

Isothiazquinolone derivative

Position 5: Improved antibacterial activity has been reported against Gram positive strain by modifying or substituting this position. It has been found that bulky substituents at this position reduce activity markedly, while other substituents result in improved activity, such as methyl and amino substituents in case of gepafloxacin and sparfloxacin, respectively.

Position 6: fluorine atom seems to be essential as it helps in binding with DNA topoisomerase enzyme of bacteria.

Position 7: The evolution in quinolones mainly arises from the modification at this position of the basic molecule. This is the position where modification can bring about the major changes in potency. Attachment of heterocyclic nitrogen containing rings results in improved activity and it also affects the pharmacokinetics of the compound. Some examples of the earlier compounds with such modifications using unsubstituted piperazine are pipemidic acid, norfloxacin, enoxacin, and ciprofloxacin, which have shown good activity against Gram negative strain of viable bacteria. Substitution with a methyl group at position 3 or 4 of piperazine leads to improved pharmacokinetics. Amino pyrrolidines also possess good activity. The other unusual type of the side chain at position 7 is a bicyclic ring system such as in trovafloxacin, moxifloxacin etc

Position 8: Modification at this position affects the *in vivo* properties and antibacterial activities, particularly against anaerobes. A fluorine or chlorine

substituent at this position provides potentially active compounds. Methoxy group at this position confers good anaerobic activity, for example in gatifloxacin and moxifloxacin. This carbon atom can be replaced with nitrogen atom with retention of activity.

THERAPEUTIC USES

The fluoroquinolones have shown efficacy against a variety of bacterial diseases and are indicated in the treatment of local and systemic diseases caused by a wide range of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, mycoplasma and chlamydia. Due to the wide array of spectrum the use of fluoroquinolones has been proposed in conditions such as deep-seated infections, prostatitis, CNS infections, bone and joint infections, and nosocomial infections resistant to other antibacterial agents.

Norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin have received the most extensive clinical trials. Norfloxacin has mostly been used for the treatment of urinary tract infections. In one study, 408 out of 417 (98%) gram-negative isolates and 58 out of 62 (94%) gram-positive isolates were susceptible to norfloxacin. Norfloxacin is active against pathogens that often require parenteral therapy, and therefore, the entire spectrum of urinary pathogens can be treated with a single oral drug. Therefore, many patients who once needed long-term hospitalization for parenteral therapy of difficult urinary tract infections can now be discharged earlier and treated with these oral fluoroquinolones.

Quinolones and fluoroquinolones are considered broad-spectrum antibiotics. This means that they are effective against a wide range of bacteria.

However, because of their risk of serious side effects, the FDA has advised that they are not suitable for common conditions such as sinusitis, bronchitis, and uncomplicated urinary tract infections, and should only be considered when treatment with other, less toxic antibiotics, has failed.

Quinolones and fluoroquinolones may also be used to treat unusual infections such as anthrax or plague. Doctors may also decide to use them for other types of infection when other alternative treatment options have failed or cannot be used.

CONCLUSION:

The fluoroquinolones inhibit the actions of the essential bacterial enzyme DNA gyrase. The details of the molecular interactions of these agents with DNA gyrase and DNA and the requirements for

quinolone-mediated bacterial killing are, however, still being elucidated. The frequency of mutation to fluoroquinolone resistance is low for many gram-negative bacteria.

The fluoroquinolones are well absorbed orally and generally achieve high concentrations in urine and stool. Serum and tissue levels of many agents are sufficiently high relative to activity to allow treatment of infections outside the urinary and gastrointestinal tracts. Although the relative contributions of renal and hepatic excretion vary among the fluoroquinolones, the half-lives of elimination are generally long, allowing twice-daily dosing.

Clinical experience with the newer fluoroquinolone antimicrobial agents is accumulating rapidly. These agents are likely to be used extensively as cost-effective and clinically efficacious alternatives to parenteral therapies in selected infections.

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